

Notes on Superfields

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1 Introduction

Let us begin with the equation

$$\delta\Phi_i = \epsilon^\alpha Q_\alpha \Phi_i \tag{1.1}$$

which is a *supersymmetry transformation* of a superfield Φ_i by a supercharge Q_α , parameterized by a spinor ϵ^α . Let us unpack this a bit.

1.1 Components of the SUSY transformation

Φ_i is a chiral superfield that depends on a spacetime coordinate x^μ , and also on two Grassman-valued spinors θ^α and $\bar{\theta}^{\dot{\alpha}}$. The index i distinguishes between flavor components; for instance, we might have multiple chiral superfields $\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots$ corresponding to different fields (e.g., quark, scalar, etc.). An ordinary chiral superfield will ideally contain a *scalar field* (bosonic), *spinor field* (fermionic), and an *auxillary field*.

The supersymmetry transformation, $\delta\Phi_i$ represents an infinitesimal change in the superfield due to a supersymmetry transformation, which relates the components of Φ_i by, e.g., transforming a scalar field into a spinor field, or vice versa.

Lastly, we have the supercharge, Q_α , which satisfies

$$\{Q_\alpha, \tilde{Q}_{\dot{\alpha}}\} = 2\sigma_{\alpha\dot{\alpha}}^\mu P_\mu \tag{1.2}$$

where P_μ is the momentum operator, $\{\}$ is the anticommutator, and σ^μ are the Pauli matrices. When Q_α acts on Φ_i , it transforms the field components within the supermultiplet. The form of the transformation depends on whether Φ_i is a chiral superfield, a vector superfield, or another type. For a chiral superfield, the transformation will act by transforming the scalar component of Φ_i (denoted by ϕ_i) into a spinor component ψ_i , or by transforming ψ_i into a derivative of either the scalar or auxillary field.

1.2 Explicit Transformations

We can expand a chiral superfield in terms of Grassmann coordinates θ and $\bar{\theta}$ as:

$$\Phi_i(x, \theta, \bar{\theta}) = \phi_i(x) + \sqrt{2}\theta^\alpha \phi_{i\alpha}(x) + \theta^2 F_i(x) + \dots \tag{1.3}$$

Applying equation (1.1), we arrive at the conclusion that the supercharge acts on the scalar field as:

$$\delta\phi_i = \epsilon^\alpha \psi_{i\alpha} \tag{1.4}$$

which transforms it into a spinor field; and, likewise, a supercharge acting on a spinor field produces:

$$\delta\psi_{i\alpha} = i\sigma_{\alpha\dot{\alpha}}^{\mu}\varepsilon^{\dot{\alpha}}\partial_{\mu}\phi_i + \varepsilon_{\alpha}F_i \quad (1.5)$$

Finally, the auxillary field F_i transforms into a derivative of the spinor field:

$$\delta F_i = i\varepsilon^{\alpha}\sigma_{\alpha\dot{\alpha}}^{\mu}\partial_{\mu}\psi_i^{\dot{\alpha}} \quad (1.6)$$

Since F_i is a non-dynamical field, it typically does not have its own kinetic term but helps in maintaining supersymmetry off-shell.

2 Auxillary Fields

The existence of auxillary fields is mandated in order to maintain the correct number of degrees of freedom (DoF) between bosons and fermions; viz., the off-shell fermionic and bosonic DoF must be matched. Consider a chiral superfield $\Phi(x, \theta, \bar{\theta})$ containing a scalar field $\phi(x)$, a Weyl fermion $\psi(x)$, and a bosonic auxillary field $F(x)$. If we count the DoF, we obtain two from $\phi(x)$, four from $\psi(x)$, and 2 from $F(x)$. Actually, since $\psi(x)$ is a fermion, it obeys a first-order equation of motion, and so the four *real DoF* are treated as just two; that is, we use $\dim_{\mathbb{C}}(\psi)$ rather than $\dim_{\mathbb{R}}(\psi)$.

In a supersymmetric action, the auxiliary field appears algebraically (i.e., without derivatives), meaning it can be easily eliminated by its equation of motion. Let's see how this works in practice with the Wess-Zumino model, a classic example of a supersymmetric theory.

2.1 Eliminating the Auxillary Field

For a chiral superfield $\Phi(x, \theta, \bar{\theta})$, the supersymmetric action includes the auxiliary field $F(x)$. The part of the action involving F typically looks like:

$$S = \int d^4x \left(\partial_{\mu}\phi^{\dagger}\partial^{\mu}\phi + i\bar{\psi}\bar{\sigma}^{\mu}\partial_{\mu}\psi + F^{\dagger}F \right)$$

Here, the term $F^{\dagger}F$ does not involve derivatives and shows that the auxiliary field F is not dynamical.

Since F is non-dynamical, we can solve for it by using its equation of motion. Consider a more general action with interactions, for example:

$$S = \int d^4x \left(\partial_{\mu}\phi^{\dagger}\partial^{\mu}\phi + i\bar{\psi}\bar{\sigma}^{\mu}\partial_{\mu}\psi + F^{\dagger}F + F\frac{\partial W}{\partial\phi} + F^{\dagger}\frac{\partial W^{\dagger}}{\partial\phi^{\dagger}} \right)$$

where $W(\phi)$ is the superpotential, which is a holomorphic function of the scalar field ϕ .

The equation of motion for F is obtained by varying the action with respect to $F^{\dagger}$:

$$F = -\frac{\partial W}{\partial\phi}$$

Substituting this back into the action removes F from the theory, leaving an action with only the propagating fields ϕ and ψ . The resulting action takes the form:

$$S = \int d^4x \left(\partial_{\mu}\phi^{\dagger}\partial^{\mu}\phi + i\bar{\psi}\bar{\sigma}^{\mu}\partial_{\mu}\psi - \left| \frac{\partial W}{\partial\phi} \right|^2 + \text{Yukawa terms} \right)$$

Here, the scalar potential $V(\phi) = \left| \frac{\partial W}{\partial \phi} \right|^2$ is determined entirely by the superpotential W , and the auxiliary field F has been eliminated from the action.

A References

- [1] D. Tong, *Supersymmetry*, (2021)
- [2] S. Khalil, et al., *Supersymmetry, Supergravity, and Superstring Phenomenology*, (2016)